

Learning Gap Assessment in Integrated Science 7 at Saint Paul University Surigao-New Site Campus

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Abstract

Science education plays a crucial role in developing students' critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and scientific literacy. However, the COVID-19 pandemic and other external factors have significantly disrupted the educational system in the Philippines, affecting the traditional modes of teaching and learning. This paper focuses on the learning gap analysis in Grade 7 Integrated Science subject and emphasized the importance of identifying students' strengths, shortcomings, and areas of misunderstanding. By conducting learning gap assessments, teachers can tailor instruction and interventions to address these gaps and improve students' scientific knowledge and inquiry skills. The study was conducted in St. Paul University Surigao which revealed learning gaps in various science competencies, such as distinguishing mixtures from substances based on a set of properties and differentiating saturated and unsaturated solutions. The findings highlighted the need for personalized and targeted interventions like skill assessment, peer collaboration, continuous assessment, and reinforcement and practice that bridged learning gaps and created a more inclusive and productive learning environment in science education. Recommendations include sustaining effective interventions, employing more instructional activities, and conducting further studies on learning gap assessments in science subjects.

Keywords: *Learning gap, Assessment, Intervention.*

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Introduction

Science education is crucial for developing students' critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and scientific literacy (Santos, 2017). However, providing effective learning outcomes in science disciplines demands more than just delivering knowledge, it needs a full understanding of students' needs and development (OECD Education, 2018). But for the last two years, face-to-face classes were not implemented due

to the COVID-19 pandemic, and it had a profound impact on the educational system in the Philippines. With the closure of schools and the implementation of various restrictions to contain the spread of the virus, the traditional modes of teaching and learning have been disrupted (Chhetri & Pokhrel, 2021). The shift to remote learning and the challenges associated with it have significantly affected students, teachers, and educational institutions across the country (Dayagbil, et al., 2021). Aside from this,

typhoon Odette (internationally named Typhoon Rai) had hit Surigao del Norte last December 16, 2021 where it impacted, a total of 2,552,312 families across 38 provinces and had incurred massive damages in infrastructure, houses, education, and livelihoods that have severe and long-term effects on the affected populations (National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council, 2022). Because of this, schools were closed for months, and this further escalated things in the education system in Surigao del Norte. This is where a learning gap assessment comes into play. Learning gap analysis in science disciplines assists educators in identifying students' strengths, shortcomings, and areas of misunderstanding for the past two years allowing them to adjust instruction and interventions to meet these gaps (OECD Education, 2018).

Moreover, in the realm of education, identifying students' learning gaps is an essential step in fostering successful teaching and meeting the needs of each individual student (Learning Ladders, 2023). Critical thinking abilities, scientific curiosity, and a thorough comprehension of fundamental concepts are especially important in science education. By conducting a learning gap evaluation in the science topic, instructors can pinpoint precisely where pupils are having difficulty or have knowledge gaps (National Academy of Sciences, 2023).

In Grade 7 Integrated Science classrooms, educators can use learning gap assessments to apply differentiated instruction and individualized learning strategies. Teachers can give modified interventions, enrichment activities, and scaffolded education by recognizing the specific learning gaps that each student has. The involvement, motivation, and academic success of students in science are all favorably impacted by individualized education, according to studies (Bae et.al, 2017).

Along with, for students' scientific knowledge and inquiry skills, integrated science education at the Grade 7 level serves as a foundation. Employing learning gap evaluation methodologies is crucial for ensuring a thorough and efficient learning experience. Finding

students' strengths, shortcomings, and misconceptions in the subject area is made possible through learning gap assessments (Majeed & Umar, 2018).

Research studies stress the significance of learning gap assessments in determining the prior knowledge and misunderstandings of Grade 7 students in Integrated Science (Aquino & De Vera, 2018). Concept maps, interviews, and pre-tests have all been used as assessment tools to uncover students' prior knowledge of and misunderstandings of scientific ideas. With the help of these assessments, teachers can effectively tailor instruction to each student, address misconceptions, and build on existing knowledge (Chin & Hill, 2018).

Besides, at St. Paul University Surigao, Basic Education department, diagnostic exams were given at the beginning of each quarter. Learning gap assessments enable teachers to precisely pinpoint pupils' science knowledge gaps. Teachers get knowledge of the subjects or areas in which pupils struggle by assessing students' comprehension and conceptual understanding (Cardino & Dela Cruz, 2020). The development of instructional strategies and resources that are specifically tailored to the requirements of students or groups is aided by the use of this information. Without such evaluation, children with knowledge gaps could struggle and regress relative to their peers, impeding their overall advancement in science education (Farkas, et al., 2016).

Furthermore, a more inclusive and productive learning environment may be created where students can build a strong foundation in science topics and reach their full potential by employing effective learning gap evaluation methodologies. This study assessed identified learning gaps in Integrated Science 7, potential variables contributing to these identified learning gaps, and learners' pre- and post-test performance for the first quarter in Science 7 students of St. Paul University Surigao.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to assess the learning gaps in Integrated Science 7 for the First Quarter of

School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the identified learning gaps in Science 7?
2. What is the pre- and post-test performance of the learners for the First Quarter in Science 7?
3. Is there a significant difference in the pre- and post-test performance of the learners for the First Quarter in Science 7?
4. What interventions may be proposed?

Hypothesis

At 0.05 level of significance, it is hypothesized that there is no significant difference in the pre- and post-test performance of the learners for the First Quarter in Science 7.

Methodology

Quantitative quasi-experimental research using a pre-test-post-test design was employed in this

study. This design aims to evaluate interventions but does not use randomization. Like randomized trials, quasi-experiments aim to demonstrate causality between an intervention and an outcome. This study was conducted on the 196 Grade 7 students at St. Paul University Surigao during the First Quarter of School Year 2022-2023. A validated test was used in conducting the pre-test and post-test in assessing the learning gaps in Science 7. The participants answered the pre-test and based on the result of it, interventions were given especially on the identified least learned competencies. Then the participants took the post-test. Frequency Count and Percentage Distribution and paired t-test were used in analyzing the data gathered.

Results and Discussions

Identified Learning Gaps in Science 7

Table 1 presents the identified learning gaps in Science 7 for the First Quarter of School Year 2022-2023.

Table 1. Identified Learning Gaps in Science 7 for the First Quarter

Learning Competencies	Pre-Test		Post-Test	
	%	Interpretation	%	Interpretation
<i>The learner...</i>				
Describe the components of a scientific investigation. S7MT-Ia-1	36.56%	Average Mastery	56.80%	Average Mastery
Recognize that substances are classified into elements and compounds. S7MT-Ig-h-5	35.20%	Average Mastery	61.90%	Average Mastery
<i>Pre-requisite:</i>				
Describe the appearance and uses of homogeneous and heterogeneous mixtures. (S6MT-Ia-c-1)	35.20%	Average Mastery	60.03%	Average Mastery
Distinguish mixtures from substances based on a set of properties. S7MT-Ie-f-4	33.33%	Low Mastery	62.93%	Average Mastery
<i>Enabling Competency:</i>				
Differentiate saturated and unsaturated solutions.	33.50%	Low Mastery	65.65%	Average Mastery
Investigate properties of unsaturated or saturated solutions. S7MT-Ic-2	37.07%	Average Mastery	63.78%	Average Mastery
<i>Pre-requisite:</i>				
Describe techniques in separating mixtures such as decantation, evaporation, filtering, sieving, and using magnet.	22.96%	Low Mastery	48.30%	Average Mastery
Express concentrations of solutions quantitatively by preparing different concentrations of mixtures according to uses and availability of materials. S7MT-Id-3	15.31%	Low Mastery	23.81%	Low Mastery

As presented in the table, the competencies with *Low Mastery* in the pre-test were considered as the learning gaps that were addressed during the

quarter. The competencies (1) Distinguish mixtures from substances based on a set of properties; (2) Differentiate saturated and

unsaturated solutions; (3) Describe techniques in separating mixtures such as decantation, evaporation, filtering, sieving, and using magnet; (4) Express concentrations of solutions quantitatively by preparing different concentrations of mixtures according to uses and availability of materials description with 33.33%, 33.50%, 22.96%, and 15.31%, as mastery levels respectively.

Pre- and Post-Test Performance of the Learners

Table 2 presents the pre and post-test performance of the learners in Science 7 for the First Quarter of School Year 2022-2023.

Table 2. Pre- and Post-Test Performance of the Learners for the First Quarter Science 7

Scores	f (n=197)	%
Pre-Test		
Poor	42	21.32
Average	125	63.45
Good	29	14.72
Excellent	1	0.51
Post-Test		
Poor	12	6.09
Average	125	63.45
Good	52	26.40
Excellent	8	4.06

The provided data represents the scores of the students during the pre and post-test. The data is divided into different categories or levels of performance: Poor, Average, Good, and Excellent. Each category is accompanied by two sets of numbers: the number of individuals who scored in that category and the percentage of individuals in that category.

For the Pre-Test, 42 individuals got scores under the Poor category, accounting for 21.32% of the total population of the grade 7 students. 125 individuals got scores under the average category, representing 63.45% of the total population. Another 29 individuals got scores under the Good category, comprising 14.72% of the total population. Lastly, only 1 individual got a score under the Excellent category, making up 0.51% of the total population.

On the other hand, for the Post-test, 12 individuals got scores under the poor category, accounting for 6.09% of the total population. 125 individuals got scores under the Average category, representing 63.45% of the total population. Then 52 individuals got scores under the good category, comprising 26.40% of the total population. Lastly, 8 individuals got scores under the excellent category, making up 4.06% of the total population.

From the data given, we can observe the distribution of scores for the pre and post-test. For the pre-test, most of the individuals fell into the average category, with 63.45% of the total population. For the post-test, the distribution remained similar, with the majority still in the Average category. The percentages in the Average category and the number of individuals remained the same in both the pre-test and post-test. In terms of changes, the Poor category decreased from 21.32% for the pre-test to 6.09% for the post-test, indicating an improvement in scores for that category. The Good category increased from 14.72% for the pre-test to 26.40% for the post-test, suggesting an improvement in scores as well. The Excellent category also saw an increase from 0.51% to 4.06%, showing a relatively smaller improvement.

Overall, based on this data, it can be inferred that there was an improvement in scores for the Poor, Good, and Excellent categories after the test, while the Average category remained consistent.

Significant Difference in the Pre- and Post-Test Performance of the Learners

Findings revealed that at 0.05 level of significance, there is a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test results ($t(196) = -6.93$, $p = 0.000$). This means that the intervention used by the teacher which utilized skill assessment, peer collaboration, continuous assessment, and reinforcement and practice was significant in mastering the competencies in the First Quarter of Science 7. As Bae et. Al (2017) stated that the involvement, motivation, and academic success of students in science are all favorably impacted by individualized education. That is why it is of utmost importance that teachers give modified

interventions, enrichment activities, and scaffolded education based on the individual needs of the students.

Table 3. Significant Difference in the Pre- and Post-Test Performance of the Learners for the First Quarter in Science 7

Scores	t	df	p-value	Decision
Pre-Test - Post-Test	-6.93	196	0.000	Reject H ₀

Table 4. Intervention Given on the Least Mastered Competencies

Least Mastered Competencies	Post-Intervention Results
1. Distinguish mixtures from substances based on a set of properties. S7MT-Ie-f-4	Average Mastery. There is an increase in the mastery level from low mastery.
2. <i>Enabling Competency</i> : Differentiate saturated and unsaturated solutions.	Average Mastery. There is an increase in the mastery level from low mastery.
3. <i>Pre-requisite</i> : Describe techniques in separating mixtures such as decantation, evaporation, filtering, sieving, and using magnet.	Average Mastery. There is an increase in the mastery level from low mastery.
4. Express concentrations of solutions quantitatively by preparing different concentrations of mixtures according to uses and availability of materials. S7MT-Id-3	Average Mastery. There is an increase in the mastery level from low mastery.
Intervention	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conducting assessments, such as quizzes or tests, educators can pinpoint the competencies requiring improvement. Conducting peer collaboration, as learners with varying levels of mastery can work together, exchanging knowledge, ideas, and support. Conducting continuous assessments in monitoring learners' progress. By conducting regular formative assessments, educators gather feedback and adjust their teaching or intervention strategies accordingly. This allows for timely interventions to address any gaps or misconceptions before they become more challenging. Continuous assessment also empowers learners to track their own progress and remain motivated. Conducting reinforcement and practice by providing repeated exposure to the competencies, learners reinforce their understanding and enhance long-term retention. Incorporating activities such as drills, simulations, or problem-solving tasks specifically targeting the identified competencies allows learners to practice applying their knowledge and skills. Through ample repetition and application, learners solidify their understanding and increase their mastery level. 	

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions, were drawn:

- The Grade 7 Paulinian students exhibit learning gap on their first quarter competencies in science.
- Intervention played as an important tool in the performance of the grade 7 Paulinian students specifically in addressing the identified least mastered competencies.

Recommendation

Based from the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations were offered:

- Paulinian science teachers should include this research as a baseline data for the enhancement of instructional delivery.
- Interventions like skill assessment, peer collaboration, continuous assessment, and reinforcement and practice need to be sustained.
- More instructional activities should be employed to improve the students' competencies mastery level.
- More studies should be taken about the learning gap assessment of science subjects.

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